

Occupational Stress in Teaching Profession: Its Relationship to Teacher's Teaching Performance

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the occupational stress in teaching profession and its relationship to teacher's teaching performance. Specifically, this study employed the descriptive-correlation type of research design which primarily employed the survey method. The research instrument used was an adapted yet modified questionnaire. Frequency and Percentage, Weighted Mean and Standard deviation, and Pearson r Correlation were used as statistical tools. Results showed that respondents had high level of occupational stress; the level of teacher's attitude disclosed that it was very high and the level of teacher's performance was very satisfactory. Results revealed that

the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the profile and the occupation stress in teaching profession of the respondents was not rejected. The occupational stress and attitudes towards the organization was significantly correlated, as well as the attitudes and teachers' performance. Similarly, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the occupational stress and teachers' performance was not rejected. Thus, an intervention program as output of the study was presented.

Keywords: *Occupational stress, Teaching profession, Teachers' teaching performance, Teacher attitudes, Descriptive-correlational research, Survey method, Educational research, Workplace stress in education, Teacher performance evaluation, Pearson correlation, Intervention program, Educational management*

INTRODUCTION

The workplace today is faced with much stress of various kinds and intensity. No one is safe from stress unexpectedly. It is a force acting on a person that causes discomfort and strain. It is a stimulus or force that acts on man, affecting him in some ways. Stress has become a worldwide concern.

Connectively, occupational stress is one of the existing stresses in the workplace in which the psychological and physical reactions generally happen to an employee as a result of their being incapable to perform their tasks competently and successfully. In the teaching profession, teachers are generally working for longer hours, as the ascending levels of responsibilities require them to make themselves even more active to meet rising expectations about work performance.

Work-related stress in teaching had been a topic that received increasing attention from every school administration and the teachers. Teachers mostly devoted their time at school meeting the huge volume of work. This was oftentimes the common complaint of the teachers since they had no time for leisure activities and family. As experienced by the researcher himself, the teacher even forgot to care about oneself that sometimes made them sick physically and suffer emotionally due to stressful works in the school. Their health was even taken for granted; they developed forgetfulness that having good health was their prior instrument for them to persist in rendering their quality service.

In other words, the success of an educational program of the school depended largely upon the effective way of the teacher's performance. Teachers were the medium and instrument who provide knowledge, instruction, direction, and meaning to all the activities of the school. Besides, among all of the different jobs, learning and growing opportunities available in a teaching profession might lead to unhealthy levels of occupational stress which hinder teachers' ways to socialize, perform what is expected, and achieve organizational goals. Recognizing the sources of stress, its effects, and symptoms was important in preventing it from becoming unmanageable or debilitating in work.

The excessive occupational stress might exhibit behavior characterized by loss of concern for colleagues and students that might lead to work dissatisfaction and low morale. This also may enable the teachers to withdraw from their everyday life and career due to excessive workloads and personal problems. In schoolwork, teachers were confronted with various problems that might affect their work-related activities. Teachers who were unskilled in coping with stress may result in low performance. With this, teacher's performance could be improved significantly if they have the necessary skills in handling stress regardless of its effects.

Constantly faced with different stressors, teachers could not perform better. However, the effects of occupational stress could be positive or negative. It is positive when the stressor serves as a stimulus to produce commitment and productivity in work. Excessive stress could threaten one's ability to compete with the teaching environment. The teachers might develop various symptoms that can harm their performance. Hence, the roles of teachers in the school system were pivotal. If teachers failed to do their part to work effectively, then quality education could be hampered. Teachers should significantly play

multiple roles aside from being the students' second parents in the school. They were multitasking resulting to increase stress. Indeed, teaching put teachers under stress if they were incapable to manage it.

According to Swanepoel as cited by Dwamena (2012) work-related stress had been a topic that had received increasing attention. Thus, the researcher was interested and motivated to conduct this study concerning the area of occupational stress of teachers concerning their attitude in the workplace since the additional demands on teachers' works grew dramatically. Being in the teaching profession, the researcher somehow experiences the pressing sense and impact of stress that relatively bombarded him with unpleasant performance and unpredictable attitude towards his organization ecologically.

Hence, the researcher created a reflective interest related to occupational stress with teachers' productivity and attitude. The researcher believed that result of this study could give ideas to administrators to ensure effective management in creating a healthy and effective organization. Furthermore, the researcher was capacitated to conduct this research since he also experienced the same. Being a teacher, he somehow encountered stressful works and dealing with the learners. Thus, he would like also to create an avenue to evaluate other's experiences like his, and what could be the particular prevention. Also, the researcher would like to know the effect of this occupational stress on the teaching performance of the respondents. The researcher had a personal deep inclination to study this topic for the reason that he wanted to assess the occupational stress in the teaching profession, delineate teachers' attitude in their workplace, and improve their teaching performance to attain continuous quality improvement of education in the city.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the following theories as Transactional Theories of Work-Related Stress, Conservation of Resources (COR) Theory, Path-Goal Theory of Leadership.

The Transactional Theory of Work-Related Stress

Lazarus and Folkman (1984) proposed a theory with an emphasis on the transactional nature of stress. As explained, stress is a two-way process; the environment produces stressors, and the individual find ways to deal with these. In this connection, cognitive appraisal refers to the mental process by which people assessed two factors: whether a demand threatens their well-being and, whether a person considers that they have the resources to meet the demand of the stressor. There are two types of appraisal: primary appraisal and secondary appraisal. During the primary appraisal stage, a person will be seeking answers as to the meaning of the situation concerning their wellbeing.

Further, the secondary appraisal is made about three implications: harm-loss, threat, and challenge. Harm-loss refers to the amount of damage that has already occurred. There may have been an injury. The seriousness of this injury could be exaggerated producing a lot of stress. The threat is the expectation of future harm, for example, the fear of losing one's job and income. Much stress depends on appraisals that involve harm-loss and threat. Challenge is a way of viewing stress positively.

Meanwhile, the Lazarus theory posits that stress is regarded as a relational concept; it is not defined as a specific kind of external stimulation or a specific pattern of physiological, behavioral, or subjective reactions. Instead, stress is viewed as a relationship of such transaction, between individuals and their environment. Psychological stress refers to a relationship with the environment that the person appraises as significant for his or her well-being and in which the demands are tax or exceed available coping resources. Furthermore, Lazarus asserted the idea of psychological stress which is embedded with specific types of emotional reactions, thus illustrating the close conjunction of the fields of stress and emotions. He distinguishes 15 basic emotions. Nine of these are negative, namely; anger, fright, anxiety, guilt, shame, sadness, envy, jealousy, and disgust. However, there are four positive emotions like happiness, pride, relief, and love. The emotions like hope and compassion have a mixed-valence (Krohne, 2002).

The transactional theory of work-related stress by Lazarus and Folkman suggests that stress is the direct product of a transaction between an individual and their environment. It is the employees' attributions regarding stressors and the resulting emotions that significantly influence their choices of coping mechanisms. The role of individuals' cognitive processing is being ignored by much of the current empirical stress (Perrewe & Zellars, 1999). In this sense, any aspect of the work environment can be perceived as a stressor by the appraising individual. Yet the individual appraisal of demands and capabilities can be influenced by several factors, including personality, situational demands, coping skills, previous experiences, time-lapse, and any current stress state already experienced.

Conservation of Resources Theory

Another is the conservation of resources (COR) theory by Hobfoll (1989) as cited by Krohne (2002) that assumes that stress occurs in any of three contexts: when people experience loss of resources, when resources are threatened, or when people invest their resources without subsequent gain. Four categories of resources are proposed: firstly, the object resources like physical objects such as home, clothing, or access to transportation. Another object resources like condition resources such as employment and personal relationships. Thirdly, personal resources for example are skills or self-efficacy. Lastly, the energy resources which means facilitate the attainment of other resources, for example, money, credit, or knowledge.

Hobfoll and co-workers outlined some testable hypotheses which are called principles. The fundamental assumption of approaches on critical life events that stress occurs whenever individuals are forced to readjust themselves to situational circumstances, may these circumstances be positive or negative. In an empirical test of this basic principle, Hobfoll and Lilly (1992) found that the only loss of resources is related to distress. Another principle is the resources that act to preserve and protect other resources. Self-esteem is an important resource that may be beneficial for other resources. Hobfoll and Lieberman (1987) observed that women who were high in self-esteem made good use of social support when confronted with stress, whereas those who lacked self-esteem interpreted social support as an indication of personal inadequacy and, consequently, misused support.

Moreover, following stressful circumstances, the individuals have an increasingly depleted resource pool to combat further stress. This depletion impairs individuals' capability of coping with further

stress, thus resulting in a loss spiral. This process view of resource investment requires focusing on how the interplay between resources and situational demands changes over time as stressor sequences unfold. Also, this principle shows that it is important to investigate not only the effect of resources on the outcome but also of the outcome on resources.

Path-Goal Theory of Leadership

According to House and Mitchell, as cited by Iravo (2013), the Path-goal theory of leadership suggests that the performance of subordinates is affected by the extent to which the manager satisfies their expectations. It holds that subordinates will see leadership behavior as a motivating influence to the extent that it means; satisfaction of their needs, depend upon effective performance, and the necessary direction, guidance, training, and support, which would otherwise be lacking, is provided. Leaders who show the way and help followers along a path are effectively 'leading'.

Moreover, Path-goal theory relates to the leadership/management-related stress variable of the study in that by using a certain style of leadership, the manager attempts to influence subordinates' perceptions, behavior, and motivation, and smooth the path to their goals leading to employee satisfaction and retention. Poor leadership leads to subordinates' job dissatisfaction, job stress, and poor performance (Watson, 2009). Besides leadership, the theory also related to the policies-related stress variable of the study in that education manager shapes the goals, systems, and policies that determine teacher's work-related wellbeing, satisfaction, and performance (Thrush, 2012).

Thus, the present investigation is anchored so that the researcher was able to find out whether the theories mentioned above are still effective to the occupational stress in the teaching profession towards teachers' attitude in the work place and teaching performance.

Conceptual Framework

This study was focused on occupational stress in the teaching profession and its relationship to their teaching performance during the school year 2019 – 2020. This study perceived that occupational stress level was greatly related to the teaching performance of the teachers. As presented in the schematic paradigm in Figure 1, shows that the treated variables in the study included the dependent variable and independent variables. The independent variables involved the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, marital status, teaching experience, monthly salary, designation/position, and employment. Meanwhile, the occupational stress of the respondents such as the stressors of employees, symptoms of stress experienced, the effect of stress, and stress management intervention was conjectured to affect the dependent variable which was the respondents' attitude towards the organization. The respondents' attitude towards the organization was assessed about ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the teacher's performance as well.

The result of this study was hoped to provide teachers an intervention program related to stress-coping strategies and management with reliable feedback, especially on occupational stress to explore

avenues for self-improvement, exposure to seminars and training, provide the school management towards improvement, improve and utilize school facilities; shed light on the contributions of the stakeholders as to what extent they could contribute towards the improvement of the educational system.

These are the variables in this study conceived to affect the teaching performance of the teachers. The schematic paradigm shows the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1. Schematic Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to examine the occupational stress in the teaching profession and its relationship to the teaching performance of the teachers in public and private secondary schools in the Marawi City Division in the school year 2019-2020.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 sex,
 - 1.3 marital status,
 - 1.4 teaching experience,
 - 1.5 monthly salary,
 - 1.6 designation/position, and
 - 1.7 employment sector?
 2. What is the level of occupational stress in the teaching profession relative to
 - 2.1 the stressors of employees;
 - 2.2 symptoms of stress experienced;
 - 2.3 effect of stress; and
 - 2.4 stress management intervention?
 3. What is the level of attitude of the teachers towards the organization in terms of
 - 3.1 ethical climate fit,
 - 3.2 organizational commitment,
 - 3.3 job satisfaction,
 - 3.4 self-efficacy, and
 - 3.5 locus of control?
 4. What is the level of the teachers' performance?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the level of occupational stress in the teaching profession?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the level of the attitude of teachers towards the organization?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance?
 8. Is there a significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the teacher's performance?
-

9. What intervention program can be drawn from this study?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the occupational stress in the teaching profession.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the attitude of teachers towards the organization.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the teacher's performance.

Significance of the Study

The study was focused on the occupational stress in the teaching profession towards teachers' attitude in the workplace and their teaching performance during the school year 2019 – 2020. The results of this study were of great importance as it served as an avenue to provide awareness on the importance of identifying occupational stress, teacher's attitude, and the level of their performance that might affect the entire educational system particularly the school organization itself.

Specifically, this study would be beneficial to the DepEd Officials. This served as a boulevard to aware the DepEd officials in reducing school forms for the teachers. They would evaluate teachers meriting their exerted efforts and undefined sacrifices in grateful contribution to produce quality education. Likewise, they could create and implement sensitivity training and stress-reduction program helpful for the teacher's mental health.

The administrators would benefit from this study since this will provide a graspable knowledge regarding the occupational stress experienced by their teachers and shall extend support in handling stress through seminars, programs, and other coping strategies. They could conduct learning action cells integrating the topics related to stress. The output of this study could help the teachers to figure out their level of occupational stress. This could help trace the symptoms they experienced if under stress, its effects. With this, they could also avoid the different stressors they might encounter. Teachers could maintain their satisfactory performance if they worked out with the stress they experienced. They might work on it to achieve positive output rather than a negative outcome on their work.

Further, the study would serve as the avenue to instill awareness among guidance counselors concerning the occupational stress of the teachers can expand their expertise in extending counseling services to the teachers as well as to the students and pupils. They might create and conduct programs and training workshops related to stress-management and may provide defense mechanisms to alleviate their hurdles and uncertainties in work, family, and self. This study will serve as a source of information on other

studies relating to stress. Other researchers can use the results of this present study to test ideas in their studies as well.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of the study was focused on the occupational stress in the teaching profession towards teachers' attitude in the workplace and their teaching performance during the school year 2019 – 2020. This study covered the secondary teachers in public and private schools in Marawi City Division that were accessible, convenient, and familiar to the researcher. It covered the respondents' profile, the occupational stress, the teacher's attitude, and their Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS) were taken to measure the level of teacher's performance.

The result of the study was limited to the data covered in the questionnaires given to the respondents. However, the honest response of the respondents was beyond the control of the researcher.

Definition of Terms

To make this study understandable, the following terms are defined conceptually and operationally.

Effect of stress. It refers to stress that can have wide-ranging effects on emotions, mood, and behavior. Equally important but often less appreciated effect on various systems, organs and tissues all over the body(<https://www.stress.org/stress-effects>). These terms are used in this study as the result of the teachers' stress in the work.

Employment. It refers to the engagement of a person in some occupations, business, trade, or profession. This study refers to the kind of employment that the respondents are under either in private or in public schools.

Ethical climate fit. It refers to a set of shared perceptions of procedures and policies, both formal and informal, which shape expectations for ethical behavior according to Victor and Cullen as cited by Pagliaro (2018). In this study, it refers to the teacher's attitude dealing with the ethical standard kind of performance in the organization morally, socially, and personally.

Job satisfaction. It refers to how well or badly the work is done. It is the collection of feelings and beliefs that people have about their current job. Somehow refers to people's levels of degrees of job satisfaction can range from extreme satisfaction to extreme dissatisfaction (Aziri, 2011). In this study, it referred to the respondent's job satisfaction reflected in their attitude and performance.

Locus of control. These terms are used to refer to a person's belief about how much power one has over the events in one's life (<https://www.chegg.com/homework-help/definitions/locus-of-control-13>). In this study, it referred to the beliefs of the respondents that they had the control to rate the extent of their effectiveness in performing their jobs even when under stress.

Occupational stress. It is an individual's adaptive response to an occupational stimulus that places excessive psychological or physical demands on him or her (Anino-Manon-og, 2005). In this study, it refers to the different stress experienced by the respondents due to excessive workloads and colleague interaction, superior treatments reflected their stressors, their effects, symptoms, and management interventions.

Organizational commitment. It refers to the behavior of the workers to stay with the organization despite all other factors. A drop in commitment level comes when people do not think the rewards are not going to be worth all the efforts (Drucker, 2008). This study signifies teacher's contentment in performing their duties and responsibilities and happily fulfilling their educational tasks and works. It helped in determining whether the teachers will stay with the organization for a longer period and work passionately towards achieving the organization's goal.

Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS). It refers to *the* intervention that will help ensure the strategic, responsive, and effective delivery of Human Resources Management and Development (HRMD) services of all levels of DepEd so that it can effectively implement a learner-centered, school-based management system and the K to 12 strategies to improve the quality of education in public schools (https://www.depedmarikina.ph/resources/downloads/manual_for_managers.pdf). This study referred to the tools used to evaluate teacher's performance.

Self-efficacy. It is an individual's belief about his ability to accomplish specific tasks (Zarate, 2015). This study refers to the self-efficacy of the teachers in doing their tasks and in accomplishing the organizational effectiveness of the school.

Stress. It refers to the pressure people feel in life. When pressure begins to build up, it can cause adverse strain on one's emotions through processes and physical conditions. When stress becomes excessive, students develop various symptoms of stress that can harm their school performance and health and even threatens their ability to cope with the environment (Newstrom and Davis, 1997) as cited by Abdullah (2013). In this study, the term refers to the teacher's perceived state of weariness as indicated in their occupational stress such as constant fatigue, moodiness, anxieties, temper outburst, tardiness, and worries. It may affect the respondents if the perceived states of weariness are not managed appropriately.

Stress management intervention. This term as used refers to the stress management in the literature that typically classifies interventions according to the 'focus' of stress management and according to the 'level' at which the intervention takes place (De Jonge & Dollard, 2002). This study refers to the coping strategy used by the teachers to overcome their occupational stress.

Stressors of employees. These terms used in this study refer to the stressors that include work overload, role problems, poor job control, lack of support from supervisors and co-workers, and interpersonal conflicts. These stressors may lead to negative psychological (e.g., depression, irritability, burnout), physical (e.g., headaches, heart palpitations, hyperventilation), and behavioral (e.g., absenteeism,

turnover, violence) symptoms or 'strains' (Schaufeli, 2001). This study refers to the different stressors encountered by the respondents that put them under stress.

Symptoms of stress. These terms used to refer to how it may be affected one's health, even though one might not realize it (Schaufeli, 2001). This study refers to the symptoms such as irritating headache, his/her frequent insomnia, or decreased productivity at work resulted in stress due to work exhaustion.

Teacher's performance. This term as used refers to the teacher's demonstrated impact on students' learning as established through student achievement test scores, observed pedagogical practices, or employer or student surveys (Locke, 2006). In this study, this refers to the instructional competence, professional and personal characteristics of a teacher measured every semester of the year. In this study, the performance is measured through a Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS).

Teacher's attitude. It refers to the total of teacher's inclination, feelings, prejudice, preconceived notions, ideas, fears, threats, and conditions. It includes attitudes physical, mental, emotional, social, and psychology that directly affect their performance (Salandanan, 2005). This study refers to the positive and negative attitudes of the teachers towards the organization relating to the ethical climate fit, self-efficacy, job satisfaction, locus of control, and organizational commitment

LITERATURE REVIEW

Related Literature

The researcher takes into consideration one of the most important issues in stress studies, its definition. Stress is an ambiguous and wide concept that is attributed to varied phenomena and definitions. The variety of stress concepts is both its characters and its deficiency. Its characteristics are the multidimensionality and coverage of a wide range of everyday-life experiences (Shahsavarani et al., 2015).

According to the American Psychiatric Association (2014), stress is described as a sense of being overwhelmed, worry, destruction, pressure exhaustion, and lethargy. Therefore, stress can influence people of every age, sex, race, and situation and can result in both physical and psychological health.

Moreover, stress is a widespread phenomenon all around during the human lifespan. All people have experienced it throughout their history and human history. Stress is one of the special characteristics of life and its presence has been much highlighted so that in fine arts and literature of all eras it has been addressed (De Raeve et al., 2007). Behnoudi (2005) defined, stress as a situation in which an individual is forced to act, and cannot bear the received mental tension. In other words, stress means the readjustment of an individual with new situations and conditions. Whenever a change occurs in life, the individual is confronted with stress.

Shahsavarani and associates (2013), define stress as any influence of internal and/or surrounding environment on living being which disrupt its homeostasis" Based on the review of the literature, stress

could be classified according to the nature of the stressor (physiological, psychological), its influence on an individual (positive eustress, negative distress), and the exposure time of stressor (acute or short-term, chronic or long-term).

Occupational stress is stress related to one's job that often stems from unexpected responsibilities and pressures that do not align with a person's knowledge, skills, or expectations, inhibiting one's ability to cope. It can increase when workers do not feel supported by supervisors or colleagues or feel as if they have little control over work processes. Occupational stress can lead to one's physical or mental state in response to a workplace that poses a challenge to that employee. The causes of occupational stress include environments, organizational climate, and a conflict that arises from the job demands of the employees. Physical symptoms of stress include fatigue, increased blood pressure, rapid heart rate, dizziness, headaches, jaw pain, back pain, inability to concentrate and confusion, immunosuppression, and chronic pain. Psychologic disorders may lead to poor work performance, higher absenteeism, less work productivity even injury. Stressful working conditions can lead to behavioral, physical, and psychological strains. Adverse health effects include psychological disorders, cardiovascular disease, gastrointestinal disease, diabetes, hypertension, weak immune system, increased risk of occupational injury, and health service utilization. Interventions to eliminate or reduce occupational stress should be both at organizational and individual levels. National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) guidelines on organizational change to prevent occupational stress is useful (Muhammad, 2015).

According to Ekzada and Tekeste (2013), the causes of stress at the workplace range from personal problems to work overload, physical working environment, work situation, and conflicts among colleagues and managers. Many employees struggle with stress, in worst cases leading to uncertainties and severe impairments on health and performance. The main situations that generate stress are likely uncontrollable, unpredictable, and some are not known. But alternatively, there are several resources available like personal awareness in coping skills. For example time management, assertiveness, ways to higher up self-confidence, and so on. Management can also utilize some resources for reducing the stress level of the employees by providing services and facilities such as health facilities at the company, giving easy and on-time access to a therapist, and also having free time activities and entertainment. Stress is related between the employee and the employer as the performance of the employee is affected by his/her stress level which in turn affects the company's productivity. However, the performance of teachers mainly depends on the teacher characteristics such as knowledge base, sense of responsibility, and inquisitiveness; the student characteristics such as the opportunity to learn, and academic work; the teaching factors such as lesson structure, and communication; the learning aspects such as involvement and success; and the classroom (International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences May 2013, Vol. 3, No. 5 ISSN: 2222-6990 421 www.hrmar.com/journals).

A phenomenon such as an environment, climate, and organization and management are important factors that affect teacher's performance. If the teachers take care of these factors, their performance can be enhanced to the optimum level (Rao & Kumar, 2004). Yet proxies implemented by states and districts to determine teacher quality have been woefully inadequate. Teacher entrance and exit examination scores,

years of experience, advanced degrees, and teaching credentials are either not related to student achievement and ratings of teacher effectiveness.

Leigh and Mead (2005) stated that teachers will have to be periodically evaluated and the compensation structure will have to be based on performance. The astringent policy will have to be developed to modernize and enrich teacher quality for hiring, evaluating, and compensating. Merit-based rewards yielded the best performance. They have indicated how quality matters by comparing the performance of students of an average teacher with that of the performance of students of an excellent teacher.

Hakanen and others (2006) used the Job Demands–Resources Model as the basis of the proposal that there are two parallel processes involved in work-related well-being among teachers, namely an energetical process (like job demands, burnout, ill-health) and a motivational process (like job resources, engagement, organizational commitment). The results confirmed the existence of both processes, although the energetical process seemed to be more prominent. More specifically, (i) burnout mediated the effect of high job demands on ill-health (ii) work engagement mediated the effects of job resources on organizational commitment, and (iii) burnout mediated the effects of lacking resources on poor engagement. These organizational changes are potentially detrimental to workers' health. Indeed, recent research has found performance pressure in professionals to be one of the most stressful aspects of their work (Cahn, et al., 2000).

In contrast to performance pressure, under utilization of skills has become a significant problem in recent years. It is well recognized that pressure results from the degree to which the environment inhibits or promotes the utilization and development of skills and abilities. Under-utilization of a worker's skill-base usually occurs when the worker is performing tasks that are often simple in nature and offer little challenge. The primary cause of under utilization is the fact that many people are over-qualified for the available positions.

Gonzales (2003) stated that the dominance of women in Philippine Education is an accomplished phenomenon. The findings imply that most women are believed to be compassionate and affectionately dedicated in their careers. They exert selfless efforts to achieve the goals of the school where they are connected. One of the respectable characteristics of women is their ability to sympathize with others and the potential to establish a harmonious relationship with people. Thus, females are more capable of handling different stressful problems encountered in the teaching work since females are hypothesized to be more relational, expressive.

Bruckheim (2002), has pointed out that stress can be brought out by both positive and negative things in one's life. Dealing with stress and knowing how to spot the things that cause it (stressors) are extremely important. People who are stress survivors stay healthy through that worst time. They consider the stressful condition as opportunities for growth. While on the negative side, such situations can include loss of appetite, children who misbehave, money problems and not enough time with loved ones, lack of shared family responsibility, and dozens of other things. Positive stressors may include positive results.

Relatively, Elliot (1993) enumerated various symptoms of stress which helped in identifying the extent of stress that a person was experiencing. Moreover, the symptoms of stress-induced illness may suggest disease in any part of the body. Patients often feel multi-symptoms including various combinations of the following: nervousness, sweating, trembling, fatigue, faintness, indigestion, headache, neck pain, and back pain, shortness of breath, and chest pain. These symptoms may reflect real disease. A heart attack is a real, threatening disease, and indigestion may represent a peptic ulcer, a very real source in the stomach.

According to Hart (2000), stress is the wear and tear of bodies experience as a person subject to his continually changing environment. It has physical and emotional effects on him and can create positive or negative feelings. As a positive influence, stress can help compel him into action; it can result in a new awareness and exciting new perspectives. As a negative influence, it can result in a feeling of distrust, anger, rejection, and depression, which in turn can lead to health problems, with the death of a loved one, the birth of a child, job promotion, or a new relationship.

According to Steddard (1993), people work harder but get less done. Everything becomes a less major effort; they do too much and do not enjoy it. They have to know when they are overdoing it. They have to recognize when it is time to do something for themselves. So, they lose control and become somebody, they rather not be around because they are under too much stress.

Mohanty (2003) said that the teacher is the pivot of any education system. Teachers are the strength of a nation. Teachers develop performance style characteristics and attitudes to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. A person is, therefore, likely to act in a way that maximizes the use of his aptitudes. Similarly, a teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determines his positive perception of the environment. Another characteristic of quality/successful teachers is good interpersonal skills.

According to Conventry (2007), occupational commitment plays an important role in the quality performance of employees. If an individual lacks the commitment to work, his performance may not be satisfactory. The behavior of an individual at work greatly matters in this effect. Most individual works better if their job is pleasant among friendly companions and in a cheerful setting. Many workers prefer routine work and remain there than to be promoted to a higher, more challenging job. Other values security rather than higher but risky positions. Also, they want to feel important or least acceptable to everybody in the organization.

Locke (2006), expounds that job satisfaction is a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. It is simply how content an individual is with his or her job; whether he or she likes the job or not.

Cayci (2011) illustrated that self-efficacy is an individual's belief about his or her abilities to produce desired outcomes. Self-efficacy is more closely related to self-concept, which is the positive or negative perception one has about his or her abilities. Self-efficacy generally refers to the trust an individual

has towards himself to produce certain tasks or responsibilities properly and effectively. Self-efficacy is an evaluation of the ability to perform a certain behavior in certain circumstances. Moreover, It refers to the teacher's assessment of his ability to organize and implement learning behavior to achieve teaching effectiveness.

Phares (1974) states that locus of control is a generalized expectancy of success that cuts across specific content areas. Personal and general teacher efficacy were both related to teachers' beliefs that they personally, and all teachers generally, could influence children's learning. Panda and Mohanty (2003) believe that the teacher is the pivot of any education system. Teachers are the strength of a nation. Teachers develop performance style characteristics to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. Similarly, a teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determines his positive perception of the environment.

Related Studies

In recognizing the different tasks of teachers, both the public and private school teachers, stress is undoubtedly inherent and regardless of other factors, the process of teaching is, in itself, stressful. Many teachers find the demands of being professional educators, especially in today's generation, difficult and very stressful in so many ways.

The study of Pagayan (2016) dealt with determining the stress profile of the public elementary school teachers in Tacloban City, specifically determined the sources and level of stress of the teachers, and their corresponding coping mechanisms. With a sample size of 267 and using descriptive – correlative as methodology, the study tested the hypothesis on the differences of sources and level of stress and coping mechanisms as grouped according to profile variables.

Additionally, the study found out that there were many sources of stress of teachers such as lack of teaching guides and learning materials, working under deadline pressures, pupils' lack of interest and poor study habits, having to deal with students' misbehavior/misconduct, and financial burden. The teachers' level of stress was generally high. Corresponding to the sources and level of stress felt by the teachers, they employed positive coping mechanisms. Though, others opted to employ negative coping strategies. There were no significant differences in the sources and level of stress as grouped according to profile variables; however, there were some significant differences in some coping strategies implying that the teachers had unique ways of dealing with stressful situations. No significant relationship was found between the level of stress and sources of stress which signifies that the level of stress did not depend on the number of stressors. It was then recommended that a classroom intervention program be developed in school to lessen the stress if not eradicated.

Moreover, the relationship between work stress and employee performance according to Divakar (2015) in his study on factors leading to work stress and its impact on employee performance, had shown the impact of the performance of the employees from different parts. And as result, its feedback was very useful in analyzing the need of the employees.

Also, work-related stress was still a developing concept but it was a reality, although the topic was covered in hundreds of papers published every year. The concept was focus on the main evidence of risk factors taken from the existing research, as concerns in particular work-related stress interventions and related costs.

In Karasek's demand-control model, stress at the workplace was a function that indicated how demanding a person's job is. Employees were over their responsibilities. This created four kinds of jobs: passive, active, low strain, and high strain. Out of the total respondents, 93% felt problems among the employees could lead to lower job satisfaction level and in that way to lower their employee performance level also. The necessity of good interpersonal relationships among employees to ensure better job performance in the work field could be understood by this analyzed data. It was also found out that the respondents had taken frequent leaves from a job due to their boredom and lack of interest in their current job. This data was pointed towards the significance of job satisfaction and employee performance and their interest to continue with the job. From the data, it could be interpreted that reduction in job satisfaction led to boredom and reduction of interest in work. The lack of interest could be reflected in their job performance level also.

Hence, the higher the job satisfaction the higher employee performance was. Thus, it could be interpreted that the level of job satisfaction was reflected in their performance level in the workplace. This data proclaimed the significance of job satisfaction among employees to get the best performance from their part.

In this regard, a recent survey of managers in the United Kingdom indicated that the majority were unhappy with the current workplace culture where they were required to work extended hours and cope with large workloads while simultaneously meeting production targets and deadlines (Townley, 2000). The results of this study highlighted a range of stress-related symptoms including excessive tiredness, headaches, and a loss of temper as being associated with such workplace demands. Further studies had established an association between increased working hours and impoverished family and social life (Cahn et al., 2000), thus exacerbating the impact of work stress.

Insight

Since the sources of occupational stress can vary from person to person, it's important to know those employees of all organizations and regardless of how big or how small they may or can be affected by occupational stress.

Most of the researches showed that many of the stressful type of occupation where those which demanded too much pressure that was not compatible to workers' knowledge and abilities, because there was no opportunity to practice any choice or control, and there was no support from others. Occupational stress especially among teachers could be caused by not properly managed work organization, by not properly managed work design, poor management; working flocks were not happy with conditions, and less support from colleagues and supervisors. In deciding the performance level of employees, the level of job satisfaction has a great role in it.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. The study was descriptive in nature since it was opted to investigate the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, marital status, number of years in service, monthly salary, designation/position, and employment; the occupational stress of concerning stressors of employees, symptoms of stress experienced, the effect of stress and stress management intervention; respondents' attitude towards the organization such as ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, locus of control and the teacher's performance as well.

It utilized the correlation design since it investigated the relationship between the profile of the respondents and the occupational stress in the teaching profession; the relationship between the occupational stress in the teaching profession and the attitude of teachers towards the organization; the relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance; and the last one is the relationship between the occupational stress in the teaching profession and the teacher's performance.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in Marawi City Division which covered 73 public schools and 45 private schools. Among the 73 public schools in Marawi City Division, 61 were elementary schools, and 8 were secondary schools and four were senior high schools. Specifically, the researcher conducted this study at the Secondary Schools namely (1) Marawi City National High School in Barangay Green besides People's Park, (2) RPMD National Science High School located at Lilod-Bliss, Papandayan the only science high school under Marawi City Division, (3) Angola National High School, (4) Marawi Pilot Integrated School now newly named as Dansalan Integrated School at Sagonsongan permanent shelter and (5) Lake Lanao National High School located at Sugod Proper, Marawi City.

Further, there were six from the private secondary schools namely (1) Jamiatu Philippine Al-Islamia from the ground zero and now situated at Barangay Bangon near the Marawi City Hall, (2) Ibn Siena Integrated School Foundation located at Prep before the gate entrance of Mindanao State University-Main Campus, (3) Al-Khwarizmi International College – Science Laboratory High School located at Basak Malutlut, (4) Philippines Engineering and Agro-Industrial College and (5) Philippine Integrated School at Bangon Marawi City besides Philippines Muslim Teacher's College, (6) Jamiatu Muslim Mindanao at Matampay, Marawi City.

Marawi City is the capital of Lanao Del Sur province in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region of the Philippines. Based on the 2015 census, it had a population of 201,785. Marawi has a total land area of 8,755 square hectares (21,630 acres). It is located on the northernmost shores of Lake Lanao and straddles the area where the Agus River starts. It is bounded to the north by the municipalities of Kapai and Saguiaran;

to the south by Lake Lanao; to the east by the municipalities of Bubong and Ditsaan-Ramain; and to the west by the municipalities of Marantao and Saguiaran. The Bagang beach is situated 2 kilometers (1.2 mi) from the city's commercial center. Thirty kilometers is the distance from Iligan City to Marawi City.

Respondents and Sampling Procedures

Respondents were limited to five (5) public schools with seventy-one (71) respondents and six (6) private schools with thirty-nine (39) respondents in Marawi City Division. Thus, the total of the respondents was one hundred ten (110) as included in the study. Only those actual teaching teachers who were itemized from public schools and regular in contract from private schools were considered as the respondents of the study. They were considered handling subjects actually during the school year 2019 – 2020. Specifically, there were a total of one hundred ten (110) teacher respondents from private and public schools. They were chosen purposively to answer the needed data for the study.

Table 1 displays the sample table to show 110 total respondents.

Table 1
The Respondents of the Study

Public School Respondents	Private School Respondents
Marawi City National High School 13	Jamiatu Philippine Al-Islamia 7
RPMD National Science High School 14	Ibn Siena Integrated School Foundation 6
Angoyao National High School 15	Al-Khwarizmi International College – Science Laboratory High School 5
Lake Lanao National High School 15	Philippines Engineering and Agro-Industrial College 8
Dansalan Integrated School 14	Philippine Integrated School 7
	Jamiatu Muslim Mindanao 6
<i>TOTAL</i> <i>71</i>	<i>TOTAL</i> <i>39</i>

Research Instruments and their Validity

The survey questionnaire was the main instrument used in gathering the needed data. This study adapted and used standardized questionnaires; yet modified following the scope of the study and the nature of the situation. They were:

A. Occupational Stress in Teaching Profession. This instrument was conducted on five public organizations. To facilitate the analysis of the instrument, it is used to analyze data, effects, and interventions. The instrument used the Likert scale of 1 to 5 where strongly agree scored “5” and strongly disagree scored “1”. However, “5” along with “4” and “2” along with “1” were combined as agree and disagree respectively to facilitate data analysis. Using the tool obtained Cronbach’s alpha of .60 considered good for this type of research.

B. The Attitude of Teachers Towards the Organization. This instrumentation adopted was refined and revised with four – phased pilot test. All measurements were made using Likert – type items. Cronbach’s alpha method was used as the measure of internal reliability. All scales demonstrated adequate reliability of 0.70.

Data Gathering Procedures

After securing all necessary permits to conduct the study from the Office of the Division Superintendent of Marawi City Division down to the secondary school heads, the researcher approached the participating public and private secondary school teachers that a study was performed in their respective schools taken as the respondents. Also, the result of the evaluation of the respondents was obtained. A list of schedules was distributed to ensure that the respondents attended the data gathering.

All the communications were signed and approved by the concerned personalities including the administrative personnel of St. Peter's College. During the distribution of the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher further explained the importance and mechanics of how to answer some parts of it. The respondents answered the questions on the teaching performance-based on their view on how occupational stress affects their teaching performance. Confidentiality of their answers was also assured by the researcher.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in computing and evaluating the data gathered.

Problem 1: **Frequency and percentage** were used to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, marital status, number of years in teaching, monthly salary, position/designation, and employment.

Problems 2, 3, and 4: **Weighted mean** was used to determine the level of occupational stress in the teaching profession, the attitude of teachers towards the organization, and the teacher's performance.

Hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4: **Pearson r Correlation** was used to determine the significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the occupational stress in the teaching profession; the occupational stress in the teaching profession and the attitude of teachers towards the organization; the

attitude of teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance; and, the occupational stress in the teaching profession and the teacher's performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PROBLEM 1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, number of years in teaching, monthly salary, designation/position, and employment?

Table 2
Age Profile of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
40-above	23	20.9
31-40	23	20.9
21-30	60	54.5
below-20	4	3.6
Total	110	100.0

Figure 2. Age Profile

Table 2 (Figure 2) presents the age profile of the respondents. Results described that nearly half (54.5%) of the respondents were 21-30 years of age, 46 or 41.8% of them were at least 31 years of age, and only 4 or 3.6% of them were at most 20 years of age. The result showed that most of the respondents were aged between 21 – 30 years of age which could be said that they were mature enough approaching the early adulthood stage.

The findings implied that respondents at their age were trailblazers to explore more on the field of their profession. They needed more experience to understand the field of their work as embodied by different kinds of stressful work. The respondents likewise had to be flexible at their age range and might be capable to handle stress regardless of its extent. There might be uncertainties and pressure they met concerning the work that usually affected them. The respondents needed to be exposed to different stressors; thus, become resilient in facing the different challenges and works despite their experienced stress personally and professionally.

This study was supported by the American Medical Association (2001), which stated that young adults were better able to solve problems, think about their future, appreciate the opinions of others, and understand the long-term effects of their decisions. However, they tended to use these skills inconsistently; as a result, they sometimes did things without thinking first. Many successfully did their work effectively when they were capable of understanding the people that surrounded them. AMS also said that early adulthood was more self-assured and better able to resist pressure in works and family matters. They spent less time than they used to with their families. They were excited and at the same time overwhelmed by the possibilities for their future.

Table 3
Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	33	30.0
Female	77	70.0
Total	110	100.0

Figure 3. Sex Profile

Table 3 (Figure 3) presents the sex profile of the respondents. Results described that majority (70%) of the respondents were females, 33 or 30% of them were males. The results showed that most of the respondents were females which signified that the teaching profession was dominated by women.

The findings of the study implied that the field of teaching was prevalingly performed by females since they were more talkative, communicative, and confident, and loved students. The findings showed that female teachers dominated the teaching force of secondary and elementary public and public schools in Marawi City Division who were conscientious and devoted to their work despite the demand in their home and family responsibilities that might cause them to be stressed. It was reinforced by Gonzales (2003), who stated that the dominance of women in Philippine Education was an accomplished phenomenon. The findings implied that most women were believed to be compassionate and affectionately dedicated in their careers. They exerted selfless efforts to achieve the goals of the school where they were connected. One of the respectable characteristics of women was their ability to sympathize with others and the potential to establish a harmonious relationship with people. Thus, females were more capable of handling different stressful problems encountered in the teaching work since they were hypothesized to be more relational and expressive.

Table 4
Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Married	65	59.1
Single	43	39.1
Widow	2	1.8
Total	110	100.0

Figure 4. Marital Status

Table 4 (Figure 4) presents the marital status profile of the respondents. Results described that more than half 65 or (59.1%) of the respondents were married, 43 or (39.1%) of them were single, and only 1 or (1.8%) of them was a widow. The results showed that more than half of the respondents were married which means other responsibilities might stress them aside from their teaching works and responsibilities.

This implied that married teachers might have rich experiences both in families and in handling students since it reflected their mother's role and care in dealing with their children and students. They might probably expect to know how to handle children to facilitate their learning. However, the fact could not be denied that they might also experience stressful situations in facing their family roles, teaching work, student's behavior, relationship with colleagues, and in being a subordinate. Besides, married teachers were faced with different responsibilities and thus, could cope with any situation that might have in their personal and teaching experiences.

Timbang (2001), said that married people could be more mature, responsible, and financially stable. With these, they became better at acting as advisers or consultants in some conflicts that might arise in an organization.

Table 5
Teaching Experience of the Respondents

Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
16-above	21	19.1
11-15	24	21.8
6-10	13	11.8
1-5	52	47.3
Total	110	100.0

Figure 5. Teaching Experience

Table 5 (Figure 5) presents the teaching experience profile of the respondents. Result described that nearby half 52 or (47.3%) of the respondents had experience in teaching between 1-5 years, 24 or (21.8%) of them had been in service between 11 – 15 years, 21 or (19.1%) were above 16 years, and few 13 or (11.8%) were 6 – 10 years in service. The findings showed that it was congruent with the result in their age range; and thus, signified that the respondents were novice and rookie which somehow stressed them to overcome the hit of hard works.

With this number of years in teaching experience, it was expected that respondents were more aggressive and competitive in teaching for they were still new in service. Furthermore, length of service had been, since time immemorial, proven to be very important in teaching amateur teachers who were eager to teach. Wide experience in teaching was vital to aware oneself from knowing their student's multiple intelligence and diversity to understand their weaknesses and strengths. The finding implied that respondents might have a narrow or limited understanding and experience on matters concerning their students and work that led them to meet stressful challenges and problems.

Indeed, Behnoudi (2005) claimed stress as a situation in which an individual was forced to act, and could bear the received mental tension. In other words, stress meant the readjustment of an individual with new situations and conditions. Whenever a change occurred in life, the individual was confronted with stress. Likewise, if the teachers took care of these factors, their performance could be enhanced to the optimum level (Rao & Kumar, 2004). Teachers' entrance and exit examination scores, years of experience, advanced degrees, and teaching credentials were either not related to student achievement and ratings of teacher effectiveness.

Table 6
Monthly Salary of the Respondents

Monthly Salary	Frequency	Percentage (%)
40,001-above	1	0.9
30,001-40,000	0	0.0
20,001-30,000	54	49.1
15,001-20,000	15	13.6
10,001-15,000	28	25.5
below-10,000	12	10.9
Total	110	100.0

Figure 6. Monthly Salary

Table 6 (Figure 6) presents the monthly salary profile of the respondents. Results described that nearby half 54 or (49.1%) of the respondents’ earned 20,001-30,000 monthly, 28 or (25.5%) of them earned 10,001-15,000, 15 or (13.6%) received 15,001-20,000, 12 or (10.9%) earned below-10,000, 1 or (0.9%) earned above 40,001, and none of them 0 or (0%) earned 30,001-40,000. The finding showed that majority of the respondents earned financially which could be consider enough for survival.

The findings implied that respondent's monthly income could be considered enough for survival especially since the majority of them were married who had other personal responsibilities aside from work. This kind of financial set-up might provide them stressful encounters with other priorities in life and thus, might also affect their job performance.

Connectively, Leigh, and Mead (2005) brought about the fact that the quality of teaching had come down gradually world over; and demonstrated that the skills of teachers had come down due to outdated preparation on the part of the teacher and stagnant compensation schemes by the management of the educational institution. This condition in the recent years for the teacher-led to (1) very few growth opportunities (2) inadequate compensation structure.

Table 7
Designation/Position of the Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Teacher I	107	97.3
Teacher II	1	0.9
Teacher III	0	0.0
Master Teacher I	2	1.8
Total	110	100.0

Figure 7. Designation/Position

Table 7 (Figure 7) presents the designation profile of the respondents. Result described that greater majority 97 or (97.3%) of the respondents were Teacher I in designation, 2 or (1.8%) of them were Master Teacher I, 1 or (0.9%) were Teacher II, and none of them 0 or (0%) were Teacher III. The findings showed that respondents were still adjusting to the demand of teaching work. The findings of the study were congruent in the respondent's year of experience since most of the teachers were the teacher I who lack more professional growth and experience as reflected for being not promoted in rank.

This implied that many of the respondents had not yet been promoted to a higher position. This was also due to the reason that most of the teachers had served for a short period based on their years in service. Teachers should enroll professionally in master's degrees or other related fields to be more appended and expert in their job performance. They must be equipped with various appropriate strategies applicable in their field of specialization. They should manage the stress which they encountered on their day-to-day life basis. Likewise, they had to continually perform better in teaching with satisfying compensation to prevent stress financially and psychologically. The thought to be promoted might also stress the respondents.

It is in line with human motivation according to Rosenberg (1980) who viewed it as dynamic because what motivated one person today might not motivate him/her at all or to the same degree the next day. Motivation as being biologically driven to satisfy personal physiological needs (e.g., Maslow's conception), biological needs played a role in motivation, much of what drives motivation to do or not do something came from the need to feel effective and demonstrate mastery of the environment. The motivation was something that initiates, sustains, and directs thinking and behavior. It caused one to act and perform his job better like teaching well.

Table 8
Employment of the Respondents

Employment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Public	71	64.5
Private	39	35.5
Total	110	100.0

Figure 8. Employment

Table 8 (Figure 8) presents the employment profile of the respondents. Results described that the greater majority 71 or 64.5% of the respondents were public teachers, while 39 or (35.5%) of them were private school teachers. The finding showed that the majority of the respondents came from public schools.

The findings implied that respondents faced various workloads since they were in the public schools compared to those in private. Teachers in public schools faced various problems which somehow increased the possibility of experiencing stress at an early stage. Specifically, they might face stress on financial, social, psychological, and cultural which was very common in meeting diverse students, colleagues, and unpredictable superior.

PROBLEM 2. What is the level of occupational stress in the teaching profession in terms of stressors of employees, symptoms of stress, effect of stress, and stress management intervention?

Table 9
Level of Occupational Stress in Terms of Stressors of Employees

Stressors	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Low/Inadequate salary	3.02±1.02	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
2. Unfair treatment by the principal	1.94±1.08	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
3. Work overload	2.30±0.90	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
4. Inadequate resources	2.77±0.98	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
5. Uncertainty about promotion	3.07±0.94	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
6. Work/family conflict	2.11±0.96	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
7. Mismatch of subjects and field of specialization	2.15±0.87	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
8. Excessive supervision and criticism	2.13±1.07	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
9. Rigid and authoritative system	2.18±1.01	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
10. Competition with co-workers	1.91±0.74	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
Average	2.36±0.62	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>

Note: 1.00-1.74 Fully Disagree (Very Low) 2.50-3.24 Agree (High)
 1.75-2.49 Disagree (Low) 3.25-4.00 Fully Agree (Very High)

Figure 9. Stressors of Employees

Table 9 (Figure 9) presents the level of occupational stress in terms of stressors of employees. Results depicted that the respondents had a high level of stress relative to uncertainty about promotion (M=3.07, SD=0.94), low or inadequate salary (M=3.02, SD=1.02), and inadequate resources (M=2.77, SD=0.98). The result implied that respondents were aiming to be promoted. It was relative to the result in their profile designation showing that they wanted to be promoted to some increasing salary position since they felt that their salary was inadequate to sustain their personal, social, and academic resources. They might be working hard yet still not promoted in the position that made them stressed highly thinking as their efforts were not paid off.

However, the respondents had a low level of stress in work or family conflict (M=2.11, SD=0.96), excessive supervision and criticism (M=2.13, SD=1.07), competition with co-workers (M=1.91, SD=0.74), and unfair treatment by the principal (M=1.94, SD=1.08). This implied that respondents received proper treatment from their superiors. They might have established a positive relationship with their superiors and colleagues that made them less stressed although somehow there might be a misunderstanding. They might likewise able to handle problems within their personal life that lessen their stress.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents on their stressors of employees were quite low with an average score of 2.36 and a variation of 0.62. It meant that respondents were able to manage somehow their sources of stress relating to their work, and other uncertainties. Bruckheim (2002) pointed out that stress could be brought out by both positive and negative things in one's life. People who were stress survivors stay healthy through that worst time. They considered stressful conditions as opportunities for growth. While on the negative side, such situations could include loss of appetite, children who misbehave, money problems and not enough time with loved ones, lack of shared family responsibility, and dozens of other things. Positive stressors might include positive results.

Table 10
Level of Occupational Stress in Terms of Symptoms of Stress

Symptoms of Stress	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Anxiety/Worry	2.77±0.71	Agree	High
2. Depression	2.68±0.91	Agree	High
3. Anger	2.56±0.82	Agree	High
4. Overworking	2.86±0.85	Agree	High
5. Moodiness	2.64±0.80	Agree	High
6. Loneliness	2.42±0.91	Disagree	Low
7. Lack of confidence	2.20±0.97	Disagree	Low
8. High blood pressure	2.18±0.81	Disagree	Low
9. Headache	2.59±0.82	Agree	High
10. Body pain due to over fatigue	2.76±0.93	Agree	High
Average	2.57±0.58	Agree	High

Note: 1.00-1.74 Fully Disagree (Very Low) 2.50-3.24 Agree (High)
 1.75-2.49 Disagree (Low) 3.25-4.00 Fully Agree (Very High)

Figure 10. Symptoms of Stress

Table 10 (Figure 10) presents the level of occupational stress in terms of symptoms of stress. Results depicted that the respondents had high level of stress symptoms relative to anxiety/worry (M=2.77, SD=0.71), depression (M=2.68, SD=0.91), anger (M=2.56, SD=0.82), overworking (M=2.86, SD=0.85), moodiness (M=2.64, SD=0.80), headache (M=2.59, SD=0.82), and body pain due to over fatigue (M=2.76, SD=0.93). The results implied that respondents experienced occupational stress which was manifested in

the mentioned symptoms. Being in the teaching profession was not that easy. Teachers experienced a lot of hard times and excessive workloads that were hardly made them incapable to manage. Teaching was the noblest profession; yet, one of the stressful work due to various encounters and experiences.

Yet, the respondents had a low level of stress symptoms relative to loneliness ($M=2.42$, $SD=0.91$), lack of confidence ($M=2.20$, $SD=0.97$), and high blood pressure ($M=2.18$, $SD=0.81$). This implied that although respondents showed fewer symptoms of stress, it did not lead to severe effects as mentioned. It might also challenge the respondents to be more confident and stronger in overcoming problems they encountered. It made them more vigorous and persistent to impart their knowledge and expertise. However, if stress were not managed properly and preventively, it might become worst and defective on the personality, behavior, self-concept, and self-esteem of a person.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their symptoms of stress were quite high with an average score of 2.57 and a variation of 0.58. Relatively, teachers were bombarded with school tasks and other school-related activities which somehow weakened their body, mind, and soul. They tended to experience various negative reactions of the body which they thought to be a minor disease or illness. Those physical reactions might be just a symptom of stress without their knowledge. The teacher must be aware of the different negative physical reactions such as headaches, back pains, fatigue, fear, and anxiety which could be just a symptom of stress.

Elliot (1993) enumerated various symptoms of stress which helped in identifying the extent of stress that a person was experiencing. Moreover, the symptoms of stress-induced illness may suggest disease in any part of the body. Patients often feel multi-symptoms including various combinations of the following: nervousness, sweating, trembling, fatigue, faintness, indigestion, headache, neck pain, and back pain, shortness of breath, and chest pain. These symptoms might reflect real disease. A heart attack was a real, threatening disease, and indigestion might represent a peptic ulcer, a very real source in the stomach. Thus, identifying one's stress also might help a teacher from dying earlier.

Table 11
Level of Occupational Stress in Terms of Effects of Stress

Effects of Stress	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Working below par	2.39±0.79	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
2. Conflict with employees	2.06±0.75	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
3. Seeking employment elsewhere (Moonlighting)	2.05±0.76	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
4. Unimproved performance	2.28±0.84	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
5. Lack motivation and easily disruptive	2.36±0.74	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
6. Lack of satisfaction	2.25±0.74	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
7. Unable to submit paper works on time	2.22±0.78	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
8. Refuse to accept changes	2.15±0.85	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
9. Low self-esteem and self-concept	2.16±0.80	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>

E10. Inefficient and Ineffective	2.01±0.80	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
Average	2.19±0.65	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>

Note: 1.00-1.74 Fully Disagree (Very Low) 2.50-3.24 Agree (High)
 1.75-2.49 Disagree (Low) 3.25-4.00 Fully Agree (Very High)

Figure 11. Effects of Stress

Table 11 (Figure 11) presents the level of occupational stress in terms of its effects. Results depicted that the respondents had a low level of stress effects relative to all the indicators such as working below par (M=2.39, SD=0.79), conflict with employees (M=2.06, SD=0.75), seeking employment elsewhere like moonlighting (M=2.05, SD=0.76), unimproved performance (M=2.28, SD=0.84), lack motivation and easily disruptive (M=2.36, SD=0.74), lack of satisfaction (M=2.25, SD=0.74), unable to submit paper works on time (M=2.22, SD=0.78), refuse to accept changes (M=2.15, SD=0.85), low self-esteem and self-concept (M=2.16, SD=0.80), and inefficient and ineffective (M=2.01, SD=0.80).

The findings above showed that the effects of stress on the respondents did not reflect timely with their occupational stress. It meant that respondents might be able to handle stress since it showed their disagreement on its effects. Although respondents were quite stressed. They performed their work with confidence and motivation. They tended to attain positive regard in recognizing their responsibilities as teachers and work with high self-regard effectively and efficiently. They managed their works and responsibilities even though they felt the symptoms of stress. They were able to look at the positive side of life, improve their performance, and able to maintain a positive self-image and identity.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing effects of stress aware quite low with an average score of 2.19 and variation of 0.65. It meant that the respondents were quite capable of overcoming their stress and faced challenges with optimism.

According to Hart (2000), stress was the wear and tear of the body's experience as a person subject to his continually changing environment. It had physical and emotional effects on him and could create

positive or negative feelings. As a positive influence, stress could help compel him into action. It could result in a new awareness and exciting new perspectives. As a negative influence, it could result in a feeling of distrust, anger, rejection, and depression, which in turn led to health problems, with the death of a loved one, the birth of a child, job promotion, or a new relationship. This meant that respondents experienced stress as they adjusted to their lives, works, and problems.

Table 12
Level of Occupational Stress in Terms of Stress Management Interventions

Stress Management Interventions	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Exercising and short walking	2.85±0.95	Agree	High
2. Healthy eating and nap sleeping	3.17±0.65	Agree	High
3. Implementation of employee training programs	3.15±0.72	Agree	High
4. Seeks counselling services	2.87±0.88	Agree	High
5. Socializing/informal chat groups	3.05±0.75	Agree	High
6. Participate in the decision-making process of the organization	3.12±0.73	Agree	High
7. Career and life planning for continuing education	3.11±0.76	Agree	High
8. Partake in school activities with initiative	3.15±0.69	Agree	High
9. Develop open-mindedness and optimistic	3.23±0.64	Agree	High
10. Unwind during vacant time	3.07±0.76	Agree	High
Average	3.08±0.55	Agree	High

Note: 1.00-1.74 Fully Disagree (Very Low) 2.50-3.24 Agree (High)
 1.75-2.49 Disagree (Low) 3.25-4.00 Fully Agree (Very High)

Figure 12. Stress Management Intervention

Table 12 (Figure 12) presents the level of occupational stress in terms of stress management interventions. Results depicted that the respondents had a high level of stress management interventions relative to all the indicators such as exercising and short walking (M=2.85, SD=0.95), healthy eating and nap sleeping (M=3.17, SD=0.65), implementation of employee training programs (M=3.15, SD=0.72), seeks counseling services (M=2.87, SD=0.88), socializing/informal chat groups (M=3.05, SD=0.75), participate in the decision making the process of the organization (M=3.12, SD=0.73), career and life planning for continuing education (M=3.11, SD=0.76), partake in school activities with the initiative (M=3.15, SD=0.69), develop open-mindedness and optimistic (M=3.23, SD=0.64, and unwind during the vacant time (M=3.07, SD=0.76).

The findings implied that respondents did many actions to overcome their stress by just letting it flow without affecting them which was relative to the result on the effects of stress. Respondents did not receive the effects of stress ultimately since they were able to make interventions in coping up with their stress. It was shown that they engaged themselves in various activities that could divert their thinking, emotions, and psychological uncertainties. With this, they would be able to handle their stress expectedly. Teachers as respondents were intelligently and professionally separated works from personal qualms. It was considered to be a prerequisite in wavering stressful events.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their stress management interventions were quite high with an average score of 3.08 and variation of 0.55. The general findings garnered that respondents were able to manage their stress and might employ management interventions that enable them to cope up with their occupational stress. Everyone had his capacity for handling stress. When a person lived with someone, he should be aware that he would be handling stress differently. Stress was healthy as long as one did not allow it to overwhelm him. Hard work is not stressful. When people's lives become unbalanced, they temporarily lose their effectiveness as explained by Steddard (1993). People worked harder but get less done. Everything became a less major effort; they did too much and did it. They had to know when they were overdoing it. They had to recognize when it was time to do something for themselves. So, they lost control and became somebody, they rather not be around because they were under too much stress.

Table 13
Consolidated Findings of the Level of Occupational Stress

Occupational Stress	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
Stressors of Employees	2.36±0.62	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
Symptoms of Stress	2.57±0.58	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
Effect of Stress	2.19±0.65	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Low</i>
Stress Management Intervention	3.08±0.55	<i>Agree</i>	<i>High</i>
Total Measure	2.55±0.31	Agree	High
<i>Note:</i>	1.00-1.74	<i>Fully Disagree (Very Low)</i>	<i>Agree (High)</i>
	1.75-2.49	<i>Disagree (Low)</i>	<i>Fully Agree (Very High)</i>

Figure 13. Level of Occupational Stress

Table 13 (Figure 13) presents the consolidated findings of the level of occupational stress. Results depicted that the respondents had a high level of occupational stress relative to the symptoms of stress ($M=2.57$, $SD=0.58$), and Stress Management Intervention ($M=3.08$, $SD=0.55$). On the other hand, the respondents had a low level of occupational stress relative to the stressors of employees ($M=2.36$, $SD=0.62$), and the effects of stress ($M=2.19$, $SD=0.65$). The findings implied that occupational stress affected respondent's performance but, it was based on their responses either positively or negatively. Respondents experienced and felt symptoms of stress but neglected to perceive its effects since they were able to cope up with it.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their level of occupational stress were quite high with an average score of 2.55 and a variation of 0.31. The general findings garnered that respondents experienced occupational stress in their teaching profession that might also affect their job performance. The work of a teacher is demanding. Thus, it provided unexpected occupational stress due to their teaching performance, workloads, and even problems with the learners which were beyond their skills and knowledge.

According to Muhammad (2015), occupational stress is stress related to one's job. It often stemmed from unexpected responsibilities and pressures that did not align with a person's knowledge, skills, or expectations. It inhibited one's ability to cope. It could lead to one's physical or mental state in response to a workplace that posed a challenge to that employee. Occupational stress should be both at organizational and individual levels.

PROBLEM 3. What is the level of attitude of the teachers towards the organization in terms of ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and locus of control?

Table 14
Level of Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Ethical Climate Fit

Ethical Climate Fit	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Follow organizational goals, rules, and conditions	3.43±0.87	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
2. Respect one’s own personal and moral beliefs	3.41±0.94	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3. Decide freely based on right and wrong	3.36±0.92	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
4. Accept individual differences in the organization	3.41±0.94	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
5. Act responsibly in the organization	3.37±0.98	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
Average	3.40±0.87	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
<i>Note:</i>	<i>1.00-1.74</i>	<i>Never (Very Low)</i>	<i>2.50-3.24</i>
	<i>1.75-2.49</i>	<i>Sometimes (Low)</i>	<i>3.25-4.00</i>
			<i>Often (High)</i>
			<i>Always (Very High)</i>

Ethical Climate Fit Figure 14.

Table 14 (Figure 14) presents the level of teacher's attitudes in terms of ethical climate fit. Results depicted that the respondents had a very high level of ethical climate fit relative to all the indicators such as follow organizational goals, rules, and conditions (M=3.43, SD=0.87), respect one’s own personal and moral beliefs (M=3.41, SD=0.94), decide freely based on right and wrong (M=3.36, SD=0.92), accept individual differences in the organization (M=3.41, SD=0.94), and act responsibly in the organization (M=3.37, SD=0.98). Thus, the respondents assessed that they had an excellent work attitude on ethical climate fit and values performance in the organization.

The findings implied that the respondents were attuned to professional ethical standards in teaching despite stressful encounters with colleagues, superiors, and the students as well. They divulged the vitality of moral development and social harmony in maintaining a positive environment. They respected social diversity, multiculturalism, and individual differences among each other which was pivotal in an organization particularly in making a decision, task performance, and in attaining the organizational goals and objectives. The teacher's attitude was ideally contemplated and manifested positively.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their ethical climate fit were quite very high with an average score of 3.40 and a variation of 0.87. The general findings garnered that respondents' attitude was aligned with the basic principles in the code of ethics for teachers. It generally involved establishing a harmonious relationship with others, maintaining moral and social development, and uplifting positive attitude with the students. The most respected profession in the world was a teacher. He is a model and is consciously imitated.

According to Panda and Mohanty, (2003) the teacher is the pivot of any education system. Teachers are the strength of a nation. They develop performance style characteristics and attitudes to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. A person is, therefore, likely to act in a way that maximizes the use of his aptitudes. Similarly, the teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determined his positive perception of the environment. Another characteristic of quality/successful teachers is good interpersonal skills.

Table 15
Level of Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Organizational Commitment

Organizational Commitment	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Ensures effective and efficient performance of duties and responsibilities	3.30±0.94	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
2. accept and comply with organizational values and goals	3.34±0.92	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3. do tasks effectively and efficiently	3.42±0.92	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
4. instill time management to participate and perform school activities	3.40±0.91	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
5. work collaboratively with others to achieve school mission, vision, and objectives	3.27±1.11	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
Average	3.35±0.92	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
<i>Note:</i>			
1.00-1.74		<i>Never (Very Low)</i>	<i>Often (High)</i>
1.75-2.49		<i>Sometimes (Low)</i>	<i>Always (Very High)</i>
2.50-3.24			
3.25-4.00			

Figure 15. Organizational Commitment

Table 15 (Figure 15) presents the level of teacher's attitudes in terms of organizational commitment. Results depicted that the respondents had a very high level of teacher's attitude relative to all the organizational commitment indicators such as ensures effective and efficient performance of duties and responsibilities ($M=3.30$, $SD=0.94$), accept and comply organizational values and goals ($M=3.34$, $SD=0.92$), do tasks effectively and efficiently ($M=3.42$, $SD=0.92$), instill time management to participate and perform school activities ($M=3.40$, $SD=0.91$), and work collaboratively with others to achieve school mission, vision, and objectives ($M=3.27$, $SD=1.11$). The findings showed that the majority of the respondents executed their duties and responsibilities as teachers perhaps committing themselves to their profession and the entire organization. Although, it might be stressful enough to manage work and duties. Teacher respondents identified themselves with the organization and wanted to continue participating actively in it. It also measured their willingness to remain with the firm in the future despite its stressful effects.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their organizational commitment were quite very high with an average score of 3.35 and a variation of 0.92. The general findings garnered on respondent's organizational commitment were highly evident as shown in the result. According to Conventry (2007), occupational commitment played an important role in the quality performance of employees. If an individual lacked commitment to work, his performance might not be satisfactory. The behavior of an individual at work greatly matters in this effect. Most individuals worked better if their job was pleasant among friendly companions and in a cheerful setting. Many workers preferred routine work and remain there than to be promoted to a higher, more challenging job. Other values security rather than higher but risky positions. They also wanted to feel important or least acceptable to everybody in the organization.

Table 16
Level of Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Job Satisfaction

Job Satisfaction	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Enjoys work with pleasure and excitement	3.22±1.10	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
2. Strengthen relationship with students and colleagues better	3.16±1.11	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
3. Attain contentment with the nature and condition of work	3.05±1.13	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
4. Love doing works without complaint and remorse	3.12±1.11	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
5. Embrace gratification of work despite the minimum salary received	3.02±1.10	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
Average	3.11±1.06	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>

Note: 1.00-1.74 *Never (Very Low)* 2.50-3.24 *Often (High)*
 1.75-2.49 *Sometimes (Low)* 3.25-4.00 *Always (Very High)*

Figure 16. Job Satisfaction

Table 16 (Figure 16) presents the level of teacher's attitude in terms of job satisfaction. Results depicted that the respondents had a generally high level of teacher's attitude relative to the job satisfaction indicators such as enjoyed work with pleasure and excitement (M=3.22, SD=1.10), strengthened relationship with students and colleagues better (M=3.16, SD=1.11), attained contentment with the nature and condition of work (M=3.05, SD=1.13), loved doing works without complaint and remorse (M=3.12, SD=1.11), and embraced gratification of work despite the minimum of salary received (M=3.02, SD=1.10).

The findings showed that the majority of the respondents were highly satisfied with their job even though stress was all around them. They were often satisfied with their work and compensation without complaining which meant that respondents' job satisfaction in their teaching profession was manifested.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing their job satisfaction were quite high with an average score of 3.11 and a variation of 1.06. Job satisfaction was rarely achieved. However, the respondents manifested this despite the stress encountered in work, family, friends, and self. Thus, Locke (2006) expounds that job satisfaction was a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. It was simply showed an individual was with his or her job; whether he or she liked the job or not.

Shann (2018) highlighted the importance of teacher job satisfaction for successful educational reform. Thus, reduction in teacher turnover and reform in education can be facilitated by identifying variables that impact teachers' job satisfaction relationship of characteristics of teachers' backgrounds, teachers' school, and teachers' compensation. Working conditions with teachers' job satisfaction is important. Teachers showed their interest in moving and achieving organizational goals than their job commitment and satisfaction increases. Teacher job satisfaction is the predictor of teacher retention and a determinant of teacher commitment which contributes to school effectiveness.

Table 17
Level of Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Self-Efficacy

Self-Efficacy	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Finish school papers diligently on time	3.15±0.90	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
2. Perform work successfully and creatively	3.33±0.90	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
3. Accepts failure and mistakes constructively to strengthen work enhancement and improvement.	3.21±0.99	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
4. Execute work confidently and reliably	3.15±1.13	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
5. Perform works capably despite problems	3.12±1.08	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
Average	3.19±0.94	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Note:</i>			
1.00-1.74		<i>Never (Very Low)</i>	<i>2.50-3.24</i>
1.75-2.49		<i>Sometimes (Low)</i>	<i>3.25-4.00</i>
			<i>Often (High)</i>
			<i>Always (Very High)</i>

Figure 17. Self-efficacy

Table 17 (Figure 17) shows the level of teacher's attitudes in terms of self-efficacy. Results depicted that the respondents had a generally very high level of teacher's attitude relative to their self-efficacy to perform work successfully and creatively ($M=3.33$, $SD=0.90$). It meant that the respondents particularly those in public schools were clothed with various school activities and works. Teachers were the busiest among them. Aside from teaching, they had also to perform written paper works which also stressed them. Yet, despite these various responsibilities, they tended to manage them and perform them better with flexibility and creativeness.

On the other hand, teacher respondents generally illustrated a high level of teacher's attitude relative to self-efficacy in finishing school papers diligently on time ($M=3.15$, $SD=0.90$), accepting failure and mistakes constructively to strengthen work enhancement and improvement ($M=3.21$, $SD=0.99$), executing work confidently and reliably ($M=3.15$, $SD=1.13$), and performing works capably despite problems ($M=3.12$, $SD=1.08$). This meant that respondents often committed themselves to their work by performing necessary tasks and responsibilities in school and in the organization, such as submitting school forms on time, regarding strengths and weaknesses to make work successfully and collaboratively, and unmining sets of problems and stresses along with the job performance.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing teacher's attitudes were quite high with an average score of 3.19 and a variation of 0.94. The findings above implied that teachers were optimistic and had powerful expectations on their ability to succeed despite the challenging and stressful work environment. They constantly felt confident of success. These types of teachers had a high sense of responsibility in carrying out any task by demonstrating an earnest effort. They represented a personal assessment of their ability to meet the standards of an organization and improve their teaching skills to achieve better performance.

The above findings were supported by Cayci (2011) as he illustrated that self-efficacy was an individual's beliefs about his or her abilities to produce desired outcomes. Self-efficacy was more closely

related to self-concept. It was the positive or negative perception one had about his or her abilities. Self-efficacy generally referred to the trust an individual had towards himself to produce certain tasks or responsibilities properly and effectively. Self-efficacy was an evaluation of the ability to perform a certain behavior in precise circumstances.

Table 18
Level of Attitude of Teachers in Terms of Locus of Control

Locus of Control	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
LC1. Accomplish jobs based on skills, interests, and fortune	3.05±1.13	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
LC2. Perform job passionately to instill values and receive a salary as the sweat of labor	3.13±1.11	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
LC3. Expect promotion due to qualifications and experiences	2.94±1.06	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
LC4. Perform work with luck to become an outstanding teacher	2.85±1.19	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
LC5. Try hard to improve performance at work	3.35±0.88	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
Average	3.06±0.95	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
<i>Note:</i>	<i>1.00-1.74</i>	<i>Never (Very Low)</i>	<i>2.50-3.24</i>
	<i>1.75-2.49</i>	<i>Sometimes (Low)</i>	<i>3.25-4.00</i>
			<i>Often (High)</i>
			<i>Always (Very High)</i>

Figure 18. Locus of Control

Table 18 (Figure 18) presents the level of teacher's attitudes in terms of locus of control. Results depicted that the respondents had a high level of teacher attitude relative to the locus of control to try harder to improve performance at work (M=3.35, SD=0.88). This meant that the respondents were trying their best to perform work effectively. They could perform their work following his will and satisfaction.

On the other hand, teacher respondents generally illustrated a high level of teacher's attitude relative to their locus of control to accomplish jobs based on skills, interests, and fortune (M=3.05, SD=1.13), perform job passionately to instill values and receive a salary as the sweat of labor (M=3.13, SD=1.11), expect promotion due to qualifications and experiences (M=2.94, SD=1.06), and perform work with luck to become an outstanding teacher (M=2.85, SD=1.19). It implied that the respondents had strongly believed that they had control over the situations and experiences that affected their lives and teaching performance that caused teaching effectiveness and efficiency.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing teacher's attitudes were quite high with an average score of 3.06 and a variation of 0.95. This implied that teacher's beliefs about the success of a student's failures or success, organization's effectiveness, and teaching strategy had a contribution to their positive attitude in teaching. It was deciphering to what degree the teachers felt like they had control over their classroom and their students. Teacher efficacy was strongly related to student achievement. Phares (1974) stated that locus of control was a generalized expectancy of success that cuts across specific content areas. Personal and general teacher efficacies were both related to teachers' beliefs that they personally, and all teachers generally, could influence children's learning.

Table 19
Consolidated Findings of Level of Attitude of Teachers

Attitudes of Teachers	Mean ± SD	Description	Interpretation
Ethical Climate Fit	3.40±0.87	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
Organizational Commitment	3.35±0.92	<i>Always</i>	<i>Very High</i>
Job Satisfaction	3.11±1.06	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
Self-efficacy	3.19±0.94	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
Locus of Control	3.06±0.95	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>
Total Measure	3.22±0.90	<i>Often</i>	<i>High</i>

Note: 1.00-1.74 Never (Very Low) 2.50-3.24 Often (High)
 1.75-2.49 Sometimes (Low) 3.25-4.00 Always (Very High)

Figure 19. Level of Attitudes

Table 19 (Figure 19) illustrates the consolidated findings on the level of attitude of teachers. Results depicted that the respondents had a very high level of teacher's attitude relative to ethical climate fit ($M=3.40$, $SD=0.87$), and organizational commitment ($M=3.35$, $SD=0.92$). The findings implied that the respondents showed commitment to the organization ethically, socially, and personally. Their positive attitudes manifested a passionate teacher regardless of their stressful encounters and glitches in life.

On the other hand, teacher respondents generally illustrated a high level of teacher's attitude relative to job satisfaction ($M=3.11$, $SD=1.06$), self-efficacy ($M=3.19$, $SD=0.94$), and locus of control ($M=3.06$, $SD=0.95$), which were often manifested by the respondents. It implied that the respondents performed their jobs with contentment and a sense of affectivity. They believed that they made changes in the classroom and the organization as a whole. The respondent's believed to have control over things could start positive changes and adoption, although, there were stressful circumstances they might face in their teaching profession journey.

Thus, the overall assessments of the respondents showing teacher's attitudes were quite high with an average score of 3.22 and a variation of 0.90. It meant that the positive attitude of a teacher could make a difference in the world of education. The most respected profession in the world is a teacher. He is a model and is consciously imitated. According to Panda and Mohanty (2003), the teacher is the pivot of any education system. Teachers were the strength of a nation. They developed performance style characteristics to their ways of relating to the world, perceptually as well as cognitively. Similarly, the teacher's positive attitude towards teaching and higher aspiration level determined his positive perception of the environment. It was universally recognized that teachers' instructional performance played a key role in students' learning and academic achievement.

PROBLEM 4. What is the level of the teachers' performance?

Table 20
Level of Teachers' Performance

Teacher Performance	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	32	29.1
Very Satisfactory	60	54.5
Satisfactory	18	16.4
Unsatisfactory	0	0.0
Poor	0	0.0
Total	110	100.0

Figure 20. Teachers' Performance

Table 20 (Figure 20) depicts the level of teacher performance. Results depicted that more than half 60 or (54.5%) of the respondents' performance results were very satisfactory, 32 or (29.1%) were outstanding, 18 or (16.4%) were satisfactory, and neither 0 nor (0.0%) showed unsatisfactory nor poor. The findings showed that most of the Marawi City Division private and public teachers were performing very satisfactorily in their teaching job.

The above findings implied that despite the different occupational stress they encountered that might affect teachers' performance, they could still manage well their time and exert efforts in doing their duties and responsibilities professionally and socially even how stressful it could be. This further implied that teacher respondents were performing effectively and efficiently in their related job tasks. Teachers performed exceedingly from what was expected from them. Their goals, objectives, and other targets in teaching were achieved and established standard performance. They portrayed positive attitudes despite all the hurdles and occupational stress. Teachers could separate their concerns from their jobs which helped them become committed to working.

According to Muzamil and Shawkat (2015), job performance assessed whether a person performed well. The performance was an important criterion for organizational outcomes and success. Likewise, Rao and Kumar (2004) added that the performance of teachers mainly depended on the teachers' characteristics such as knowledge base, sense of responsibility, and inquisitiveness. The students' characteristics such as the opportunity to learn, and academic work; the teaching factors such as lesson structure, and communication; the learning aspects such as involvement and success; and the classroom were considered. If the teachers took care of these factors, their performance could be enhanced to the optimum level.

Table 21 on the next page indicates the relationship between the profile and the occupational stress in the teaching profession of the respondents. Results revealed that there were no significant relationships between the profile and the level of occupational stress since the observed p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. The results suggested that the level of occupation stress encountered by the teachers was not associated with their age, sex, marital status, teaching experience, monthly salary, designation, and employment. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the profile and the occupation

stress in the teaching profession of the respondents was not rejected. Teachers had a lot of works to do in the school. They performed it better even if they did have existing personal uncertainties and hurdles. They tended to separate work from their issues.

PROBLEM 5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the occupational stress in the teaching profession?

Table 21
Relationship¹ Between the Profile and Occupational Stress in Teaching Profession

Profile	Occupational Stress			Remarks
	Mean ± SD	r-value	p-value	
<i>Age</i>				
40-above	2.46±0.39	-0.150 ^{ns}	0.118	<i>Not significant</i>
31-40	2.66±0.35	0.181 ^{ns}	0.059	<i>Not significant</i>
below-30 ^{rc}	2.54±0.25	--	--	
<i>Sex</i>				
Female	2.52±0.31	-0.122 ^{ns}	0.205	<i>Not significant</i>
Male ^{rc}	2.61±0.30	--	--	
<i>Marital Status</i>				
Married	2.53±0.34	-0.09 ^{2ns}	0.341	<i>Not significant</i>
Single	2.57±0.25	0.065 ^{ns}	0.501	<i>Not significant</i>
Married ^{rc}	2.78±0.00	--	--	
<i>Teaching Experience</i>				
16-above	2.48±0.38	-0.104 ^{ns}	0.278	<i>Not significant</i>
11-15	2.54±0.23	-0.016 ^{ns}	0.865	<i>Not significant</i>
6-10	2.63±0.48	0.091 ^{ns}	0.345	<i>Not significant</i>
1-5 ^{rc}	2.56±0.25	--	--	
<i>Monthly Salary</i>				
≥ 20,001	2.58±0.33	0.100 ^{ns}	0.301	<i>Not significant</i>
15,001-20,000	2.44±0.26	-0.140 ^{ns}	0.146	<i>Not significant</i>
10,001-15,000	2.53±0.29	-0.034 ^{ns}	0.724	<i>Not significant</i>
≤ 10,000 ^{rc}	2.59±0.31	--	--	
<i>Designation</i>				
Teacher I	2.55±0.31	0.054 ^{ns}	0.574	<i>Not significant</i>
Teacher II/MT I ^{rc}	2.45±0.30	--	--	
<i>Employment</i>				
Public	2.53±0.33	-0.085 ^{ns}	0.380	<i>Not significant</i>
Private ^{rc}	2.58±0.27	--	--	

Note: 1-based on Biserial Correlation
 ns-not significant at 0.05 level
 rc-reference category

The findings implied that the profile of the respondents had no effect and relationship on the level of any occupational stress encountered and experienced by the respondents. Their socioeconomic background, the compensation they received, their tenure of security, and work experienced were not considered as a source of occupational stress. Henceforth, Pagayan (2016) in his study revealed that the stress profile of the public elementary school teachers determined the sources and level of stress of the teachers and their corresponding coping mechanisms. The teachers' level of stress was generally high. Corresponding to the sources and level of stress felt by the teachers, they employed positive coping mechanisms. Though, others opted to employ negative coping strategies. There were no significant differences in the sources and level of stress as grouped according to profile variables. Likewise, no significant relationship was found between the level of stress and sources of stress which signified that the level of stress did not depend on the number of stressors. It was then recommended that a classroom intervention program be developed in school to lessen the stress if not eradicated.

PROBLEM 6. Is there a significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the attitude of teachers towards the organization?

Table 22
Relationship² Between the Occupational Stress in Teaching Profession and Attitude of Teachers towards the Organization

Occupational Stress	Attitude of Teachers		Remarks
	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Stressors of Employees	0.302**	0.001	<i>Significant</i>
Symptoms of Stress	-0.215*	0.024	<i>Significant</i>
Effect of Stress	-0.285**	0.003	<i>Significant</i>
Stress Management Intervention	0.295**	0.002	<i>Significant</i>

Note: 2-based on Pearson Correlation **-significant at 0.01 level
 *-significant at 0.05 level

Table 22 depicts that the occupation stress relative to the stressors of employees ($r=0.302$, $p=0.001$), symptoms of stress ($r=-0.215$, $p=0.024$), effect of stress ($r=-0.285$, $p=0.003$), and stress management intervention ($r=0.295$, $p=0.002$) were significantly correlated to the attitudes of the teachers towards the organization. Teachers having a high level of symptoms of stress and effects of stress tended to have a lower level of attitudes towards the organization. In addition, the teachers having high-stress management intervention had a high level of attitudes towards the organization. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between occupational stress and attitudes towards the organization was rejected.

The findings implied that when teachers were experiencing occupational stress, they performed less more than what was expected from them. They might show unusual reactions and negative attitudes towards the organization when they were under stress. Although they had some stress intervention management, it did not guarantee that the effect of stress could not be manifested in their job performance

and commitment. The effects of stress might also be reflected in teacher’s performance, their locus of control in performing their beliefs; and their self-efficacy might be less effective and efficient.

The American Psychiatric Association (2014) claimed that stress was a sense of being overwhelmed, worry, destruction, press, exhaustion, and lethargy. Therefore, stress could influence people in every situation and could result in both physical and psychological health. Thus, their attitude might be affected depending on the process of their reaction towards a certain stressor as it affected their thinking, beliefs, attitudes, and perceptions.

PROBLEM 7. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher’s performance?

Table 23
Relationship² Between the Attitude and Teachers’ Performance

Attitude	Teachers’ Performance		Remarks
	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Ethical Climate	0.211*	0.027	<i>Significant</i>
Organizational Commitment	0.170	0.075	<i>Not significant</i>
Job Satisfaction	0.192*	0.044	<i>Significant</i>
Self-efficacy	0.294**	0.002	<i>Significant</i>
Locus of Control	0.211*	0.027	<i>Significant</i>
Total Measure	0.226*	0.017	<i>Significant</i>

Note: ²-based on Pearson Correlation **-significant at 0.01 level
 *-significant at 0.05 level

Table 23 depicts that the attitudes of the respondents relative to ethical climate ($r=0.211$, $p=0.027$), job satisfaction ($r=0.192$, $p=0.044$), self-efficacy ($r=0.294$, $p=0.002$), and locus of control ($r=0.211$, $p=0.027$) were positively correlated to their teaching performance. This result showed that the teachers had experienced a better ethical climate, high job satisfaction, high self-efficacy, and high locus of control, the more they had better teaching performance. However, no correlation was found between the organizational commitment and teachers' performance ($r=0.170$, $p=0.075$). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the attitudes and teachers' performance was rejected.

The findings above implied that the teacher's attitude was reflected in his work performance. They performed better if they felt contented and satisfied with the nature of work they had and the positive climate they were placed in. If they felt compassionate and efficient, they could be more predictive and well-performing. However, their commitment to the work had nothing to do with their attitude since commitment lies along their duties to be fulfilled to attain organizational goals and objectives. The factors of performance were the extent to which a teacher could accomplish the tasks that made up his or her job. A mentor served as a record of outcomes he produced during a specific job, over a specific time. Teachers’ performance served as the amount of effort, initiative and absenteeism, maintenance of standards, and commitment displayed by teachers while performing their teaching tasks.

In Karasek's demanded control model, employees were over their responsibilities. The necessity of good interpersonal relationships among employees to ensure better job performance in the work field could be understood by this analyzed data. It was also found out that the respondents had taken frequent leaves from a job due to their boredom and lack of interest in their current job. Hence, the higher the job satisfaction, self-efficacy, locus of control, and climate fit, the higher the employee's performance. The data proclaimed the significance of teacher's attitudes among employees to get the best performance from their part.

PROBLEM 8. Is there a significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the teacher's performance?

Table 24
Relationship² Between the Profile and Occupational Stress in Teaching Profession and Teachers' Performance

Occupational Stress	Teachers' Performance		Remarks
	<i>r-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	
Stressors of Employees	0.217*	0.023	<i>Significant</i>
Symptoms of Stress	-0.143	0.137	<i>Not Significant</i>
Effect of Stress	-0.030	0.758	<i>Not significant</i>
Stress Management Intervention	0.157	0.102	<i>Not significant</i>
Total Measure	0.095	0.324	Not significant

Note: 2-based on Pearson Correlation *-significant at 0.05 level

Table 24 displays that the stressors of employees were significantly associated with the teachers' performance ($r=0.217, p=0.023$). The results suggested that the more the respondents could overcome their stressors at work, the more they could perform better in their teaching job. However, the occupation stress relative to symptoms of stress, effect of stress, and stress management interventions were not associated with their teachers' performance since the observed p-values exceeded at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between occupational stress and teachers' performance was not rejected.

The findings implied that the employee's source of stress had to be recognized since it affected their level of performance. It was evident from the findings that they could manage their stress and its effect yet, unable to control the different sources of stress. Hence, their performance was inevitable depending on the risks and level of sources of stress around them.

Moreover, the relationship between work stressors and employee's performance according to Divakar (2015) showed the impact of the performance of the employees from different parts. Work-related stress was still a developing concept but it was a reality. According to Ekzada and Tekeste (2013), the causes of stress at the workplace ranged from personal problems to work overload, physical working environment, work situation, and conflicts among colleagues and managers. Many employees struggle with stress, in worst cases leading to uncertainties and severe impairments on health and performance.

PROBLEM 9. What intervention program can be drawn from this study?**A PROPOSED TRAINING PROGRAM FOR STRESS-COPING STRATEGIES**

This portion anchors the training program developed based on the findings of this study. It intends to show that a stress-coping strategies program is necessary for the organizational system. The program should meet the needs of the teachers and other employees, particularly those in the teaching profession

- A. Title of the program: “Dealing with Occupational Stress and Enhancing Positive Attitudes and Job Performance”
- B. Kind of Training Program: Learning Action Cell Integration Program
- C. Date of Training Program: First Week of June
- D. The venue of Training Program: (For Arrangement)
- E. Recommended for implementation by all school administrators with the teachers

Rationale

This training program is based on the findings of the study entitled "OCCUPATIONAL STRESS IN TEACHING PROFESSION TOWARDS TEACHERS' ATTITUDE IN THE WORKPLACE AND THEIR TEACHING PERFORMANCE". The teachers must be enlightened on the level of occupational stress that may affect their attitude towards the organization and their performance as well. This program constitutes a series of well-planned and organized areas of concern and activities carefully selected to suit varying levels, interests, and needs of the teachers. The main thrust of this program is to broaden teacher's occupational stress-coping capabilities, thereby enhancing their positive attitudes and job performance. It is pivotal for the teachers to realize that experiencing occupational stress may affect the entire organization particularly in performing their responsibilities toward their job. Thus, this occupational stress-coping program serves as a wake-up call to all the personalities in the education and organizational system in enhancing their knowledge and skills in coping with work-related stress.

Assumptions

The primary goal of this training program is to enhance positive attitude and performance through a better stress coping-strategy. This program provides a vital link to the total instructional program of the public and private schools in the Marawi City division. All private and public-school teachers are entitled to participate in the Learning Action Cell in this program are entitled to join and participate and shall recognize the valuable insights of the theme "Dealing with Occupational Stress and Enhancing Positive Attitudes and Job Performance". The participants will pay the registration fee which includes a seminar kit, certificates of attendance, and lectures. The participants prefer to live out training and will just collaborate with the amount of contribution for the stay, food, and transportation.

Objectives

The occupational stress-coping strategies program is designed to create a positive defense mechanism against work-related stress and shall establish a positive attitude and build a performance that aligns with the goal of the education.

At the end of the program, the participants are expected to:

- a. understand the nature of the self, colleagues, work environment, the sources of stress, and its effects as a whole.
- b. increase their awareness of the different sources of occupational stress that may affect job performance;
- c. improve their skills in teamwork building, intergroup activities, and organizational development.
- d. identify the different problems that serve as stressors
- e. remind themselves about the diversity of behaviors of an individual because from time to time they are dealing with another individual with different behaviors.
- f. anticipate the effect of too much stress and minimize the negative ones
- g. acquire an effective occupational stress-coping strategy;
- h. increase their capabilities to respond positively to stressful work situations;
- i. relay information on how to avail free subscriptions of journals and magazines that published about stress; and
- j. improve their job performance by upgrading their attitudes towards the people around them optimistically.

Emphasis of the program

This coping strategies program shall be pursued within the context of total human resources development. The training program is a wake-up call for employees and school administrators who have done nothing to improve and enhance their personal growth, interpersonal relationship skills, and self-management skills. It shall expose them to effective occupational stress-coping strategies. It will seek to provide them with adequate knowledge on the different sources of stress and how this affects their attitude towards the organization and job performance.

Moreover, the participants are expected to broaden their horizons so that they will become more productive, efficient, diligent, and hardworking in their schools. As a result, they will become a catalyst to community development and national development as a whole. Especially, this program shall have (3) three vital emphases namely occupational stress, teacher's attitude towards the organization, and job performance.

Methodology

A steering committee shall be organized to make alterations in the implementation of this training program. The said committee shall select resource speakers and specialists who have the necessary

experience, expertise, and advanced training on stress-coping strategies. These resource persons shall come from various fields who shall have the contribution of expertise helpful to attain the program's goals and objectives.

Workshops, a video showing, and write shops shall be used to enrich the basic approaches employed in the different stress-coping strategies of the training program. The film showing shall cover all the topics offered so that participant's needs and training program objectives will be met. The following are different phases with their corresponding methodologies.

PHASES	METHODOLOGIES
A. Occupational Stress (stressors of employees, symptoms, and its effects)	Lectures, Panel Discussions, Buzz Sessions, Reports, and Case Study
B. Attitude towards the organization (ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, locus of control)	Lectures, Panel Discussions, Reports, Case Study, problem-solving approach, open forum
C. Job performance	Lectures, Panel Discussions, Reports, Case Study, problem-solving approach
D. Stress Coping Strategies	Lectures, Panel Discussions, Reports, Case Study, problem-solving approach, open forum
E. Defense Mechanisms	Lectures, Panel Discussions, Reports, Case Study, problem-solving approach, open forum, group dynamics
F. Occupational Stress Experts (Guidance counselors, psychologists, psychiatrist, and others)	Lectures, Panel Discussions, Reports, Case Study, problem-solving approach, open forum

The training program is based on the deductive training approach since the participants will have an opportunity of making generalizations according to the experience that they may get during the training sessions.

Evaluation

All the evaluation of this program shall be done in such a way that the participants will be rated on the various aspects of stress-coping strategies to determine whether they have an increased understanding of occupational stress, job-related performance, and capability to cope with stress. Evaluation sheets shall be distributed to all participants at the end of the training period to let them say something about administration, refreshments, speakers, facilitators, participants, and other comments, remarks, weaknesses, strengths, and suggestions for future references.

SUMMARY

This study aimed to determine the relationship of occupational stress to teacher's attitudes towards the organization and the job performance of the selected private and public schools in the Marawi City Division. This study also sought to describe the respondent's profile, the level of their occupational stress, attitudes, and job performance.

A sample of 110 respondents was purposively selected to complete the data gathering procedure. This study was conducted during the school year of 2019 – 2020. The study aimed to answer the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, marital status, number of years in teaching, monthly salary, designation/position, and employment status? (2) What is the level of the occupational stress in the teaching profession in terms of stressors of employees, symptoms of stress, effect of stress, and stress management intervention (3) What is the level of attitude of the teachers towards the organization in terms of ethical climate fit, organizational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and locus of control? (4) What is the level of the teachers' performance? (5) Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the level of occupational stress in the teaching profession? (6) Is there a significant relationship between the occupational stress in the teaching profession and the level of the attitude of teachers towards the organization (7) Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance? (8) Is there a significant relationship between occupational stress in the teaching profession and the teacher's performance? and (9) What intervention program can be drawn from this study?

The study used the descriptive-correlational research design in describing the profile of the respondents, their occupational stress, attitudes, and job performance. This study utilized an adapted standardized instrument from the established research; yet modified by the current researcher to fit into the needed study. Several statistical tools such as frequency and percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson r Correlation were utilized in the analysis of the data.

For the significant relationship analysis, the result revealed that there were no significant relationships between the profile and the level of occupational stress since the observed p-values exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the profile and the occupation stress in the teaching profession of the respondents was not rejected.

As to the relationship analysis between the occupational stress and teacher's performance, the result depicted that the occupation stress relative to the stressors of employees, symptoms of stress, effect of stress, and stress management intervention were significantly correlated to the attitudes of the teachers towards the organization. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between occupational stress and attitudes towards the organization was rejected.

Additionally, the relationship between the attitude of the teachers towards the organization and the teacher's performance resulted that the attitudes of the respondents relative to ethical climate, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and locus of control, which were positively correlated to their teaching

performance. However, no correlation was found between organizational commitment and teachers' performance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the attitudes and teachers' performance was rejected.

Lastly, the relationship between occupational stress and the teacher's performance displayed that the stressors of employees were significantly associated with the teacher's performance. However, the occupation stress relative to symptoms of stress, the effect of stress, and stress management intervention were not associated with their teachers' performance since the observed p-values exceeded at the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between occupational stress and teachers' performance was not rejected.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings presented in the preceding section, the following conclusions were drawn.

Female teachers were dominant in the teaching profession aged 21 – 30 and the majority were married. It can be concluded that respondents being new in the field of teaching needs a lot of experience to absorb the working condition and environment. Since they were teachers, I tried to perform better to aim for promotion and salary increase. They were the majority in public schools than in private schools which can be concluded that respondents had the chance to be stress and experience hurdles to overcome paper works and overload of personal, work, and social liabilities.

The occupational stress of the respondents was quite high. Respondents experienced the symptoms and effects of stress yet learned to manage them in their quiet ways. They also experienced the sources of stress related to the changes in their moods and emotions. Thus, the respondents overcame stress-related works to avoid its effect. Naturally, teaching is the hardest profession since teachers dealt with their environment, colleagues, students, parents, and the entire stakeholders which seemed to be the common stressors. If this may not be pressed with attention, it may lead to psychological, health, physical, social and emotional sickness in which teachers are not minded.

Results disclosed that teacher's attitudes were quite high which can be concluded that the respondents show commitment to the organization ethically, socially, and personally. Their positive attitude manifests a passionate teacher regardless of their stressful encounters and glitches in life. They perform their jobs with contentment and a sense of affectivity. They believed they make changes in the classroom and the organization as a whole. The respondents believed to have control over things that could start positive changes and adoption although there were stressful circumstances; they might face in their teaching profession journey. Thus, the positive attitude of a teacher could make a difference in the world of education.

With the respondents' performance result to be very satisfactory, it can be concluded that they perform their duties and responsibilities satisfactorily by providing the needs of the students and attaining the organizational goals and objectives. Thus, teacher's performance shows a positive result and satisfying

service in meeting the needs of the students and the school particularly the community as well as providing quality products of education.

It can likewise be concluded that teachers can perform better even under stress since they had an organizational commitment to fulfill and perform. Although the effect of stress, its symptoms were evident to the respondent's response, still they were able to apply intervention management to overcome stress across any level. Also, the teacher's attitude had something to do with their performance so the way they perceive their organization as to their satisfaction, locus of control, and self-efficacy inevitably provided positive performance aligned with what an organization should attain. Thus, it is concluded that teachers can perform better if they can attain mental health awareness related to the effect of occupational stress.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following are formulated as recommendations.

1. The DepEd Officials should reduce school forms to be accomplished by the teachers. They should evaluate teachers meriting their exerted efforts and undefined sacrifices in grateful contribution to produce quality education.
2. The administrators must have a clear knowledge regarding the occupational stress experienced by their teachers for them to help and support the teachers in handling stress through seminars, programs, and other coping strategies. Likewise, they should create and implement sensitivity training and stress-reduction program helpful for the teacher's mental health. They should conduct a Learning Action Cell related to stress.
3. The teachers should be able to figure occupational stress concerning their teaching efficiency. They should attend different interventions such as individual and group counseling, participate in outdoor activities, and maintain an interpersonal relationship with colleagues to attain a positive attitude in the organization.
4. The awareness of the guidance counselors concerning the occupational stress of the teachers should expand their expertise in extending counseling services to the teachers as well as to the students and pupils. They should create and conduct programs and training workshops related to stress-management and should provide defense mechanisms to alleviate their hurdles and uncertainties in work, family, and self.
5. This study could serve as a source of information on other studies relating to stress. Other researchers could use the results of this present study to prove or disprove ideas in their studies as well.

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